

Impact of Performance Metrics in AI Model Evaluation

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Abstract

The selection of a performance metric for the purpose of evaluating a model is not as trivial as it may appear. On one hand, the model commissioners' expectations of the model's contribution to their business objective (s) often lack empirical support. On the other hand, the model developers can easily be confused by the multitude of quantitative metrics recommended by the statistical literature for a given use case. Hence the need for a methodology that can guide the effective selection of statistical performance metrics during model evaluation. In Salami et al (2024), we considered a fraud detection use case, and we showed that F-beta ($F_\beta, \beta > 1$) is more appropriate than F_1 or the Area Under the Precision Recall Curve (AUPRC) metric in measuring the model's contribution to the business objective. In this paper, we examine two facets of the F_β , namely the weighted F_β and the un-weighted F_β and discuss how the selection of one in lieu of the other can lead to erroneous decisions with adverse impacts. As the use of quantitative models in general, and AI algorithms in particular, becomes more prevalent in decision making, our paper brings a new perspective to the performance evaluation of AI models.

Key Words: artificial intelligence, machine learning, performance evaluation, performance metrics, model testing, model monitoring.

1. Introduction

Organizations have been using quantitative models to inform or support decisions for decades. Initially developed in 1960s, the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) has been widely used to help relate the required return on an investment to the risk of that investment [2]. The release of the FICO score in 1990s has helped generalize the use of quantitative models in consumers' credit risk assessment [3].

In these cases, and many others, the appeal of the quantitative models lies on the promise that they can provide a data-driven, rational, and consistent approach to business decision-making. Given the recent emergence and popularity of artificial intelligence (AI) systems, and their ability to use powerful algorithms to process large quantity of data, the reliance on quantitative methods to inform or support decisions will only increase across organizations. However, the communication between the data scientist developing the model and the business leaders commissioning or using the model is often limited to the collection of high-level

business requirements and a limited understanding of the business process that is being represented by the model.

In this paper, we argue that this limited communication can lead to ineffective models that may not suit their purpose. During the model development phase, data scientists should not work in silos with limited information about the business process they are modeling. Rather, they should work closely with the model's owner and users to clearly understand how they define success for their business process and incorporate this definition in the model evaluation.

2. Literature Review

Research on model evaluation covers various methodologies often employed to assess the acceptability of the model output. Whether the model evaluation involves back-testing, sensitivity analysis, scenario analysis or stress testing many researchers often rely on generic statistical performance metrics, some of which are described in sections 2.1 below. But these researchers often omit to mention how these statistical performance metrics can differ from the business key performance indicators (KPI) that measure success from the business leaders' perspective. This omission reflects a serious misalignment of incentives that may occur between the objectives of the model developer on one hand and the model's owner or users on the other. This paper is trying to address this misalignment.

2.1 Statistical Performance Metrics

The statistical metrics required to evaluate a model performance often depend on the model types. In general, models can be grouped into two broad categories namely classification and regression models. In this paper, we will focus on classification models.

Classification models are used to predict outcomes that are categorical in nature. An example of classification model is one that predicts whether a customer applying for a financial product (credit card, deposit, or loan account etc.) should be approved or rejected. For such models, the literature recommends several statistical performance metrics to evaluate how well the model can distinguish between the possible categories (approved or rejected, in this case).

For a binary classifier (i.e. two possible categories), the following metrics are often recommended:

- $Recall = \frac{t_p}{t_p + f_n}$ (1)
- $Precision = \frac{t_p}{t_p + f_p}$ (2)
- $Accuracy (ACC) = \frac{t_p + t_n}{t_p + f_p + t_n + f_n}$ (3)

where t_p , f_p , t_n , and f_n are the numbers of true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives, respectively, and

- $F_1 = 2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall}$ (4)

Additional metrics include:

- the area under the receiver operating curve (AUROC)
- the area under the precision-recall curve (AUPRC).

2.2 Business Key Performance Indicators

The data scientist(s) who develop a model are in most cases not its primary users. Like a software developer whose product is often consumed by staff with varying level of coding skills, the data scientists develop models that are often used by staff with limited to no quantitative skills to help meet a broader business objective. In fact, in many business organizations, the model output is just one out of several pieces of information that contribute to the final outcome, be it prediction, recommendation, or decision; see figure 0 below.

Figure 0: Models in business decision-making

As such, the indicators of success that appeal to the business leaders (criterion #1) can be very different from the statistical performance metrics (criterion #2) that the data scientists care about.

Examples of KPIs	
Business Objective	Business KPI
Reduce credit card fraud risk	credit card fraud loss
Improve customer satisfaction	Net promoter score
Increase staff retention	Employee survey score

Table 1: Examples of selecting a business KPI given a business objective

Table 1 shows examples of KPI corresponding to some business objectives. For example, to meet the business objective of reducing credit card fraud risk, the business leaders may track credit card loss amount (criterion #1) whereas the data scientists would be more interested in the model’s discriminatory power i.e., the model’s ability to distinguish a valid transaction from a fraudulent one (criterion #2).

3. Our Proposal

The use of different performance metrics by the data scientists and the business leaders is a problem that can have serious consequences for the business when

these metrics contradict each other. From the data scientists who may spend significant amount of time and resources in roots cause analysis to the business leaders who may embark in uninformed post-model adjustments, lack of trust in the model output can become the central issue. To remedy this problem, we proposed in Salami et al (2024) to establish a relationship between the model’s statistical performance metric (criterion #2) and the business KPI (criterion #1) such that deterioration or improvement in the business KPI can be traced back to the model. This paper builds upon that proposal and provides further insight into the selection of the statistical metric to link to the business KPI.

4. An Illustrative Example

4.1 Model Description

Credit card fraud is a serious problem for banks and other lenders. A 2021’s report by the Federal Trade Commission found credit card fraud to be the second most reported identity theft type in the U.S behind government documents and benefits fraud [4]. Nilson, a leading publication covering payment systems estimated the losses associated with credit card fraud to be \$32 billion worldwide, \$12 billion of which were incurred in the US in 2021 [5]. It follows that detecting and preventing credit card fraud is a top risk management objective for card’s issuers and processors as well as merchants.

In this paper, we illustrate our proposal with credit card fraud data publicly available on Kaggle.com. The anonymized dataset, released by Vesta Corporation as part of an open data science competition can be summarized as follows:

- Number of unique transactions: 590,540 including 20,663 fraud cases
- 394 variables including transaction status, transaction date, product code, transaction amount, IP address, number of days between transactions and more.
- The target variable is the transaction status, labeled as “IsFraud”. It takes the value:
 - 1 if the transaction is fraudulent.
 - 0 otherwise.

After data preparation and cleaning, we split the dataset into training data (53%), out-of-sample or test data (23%) and out-of-time or monitoring data (24%). Then, through feature engineering, we reduced the number of variables from 394 to 48. Finally, we fit the following random forest classifier after a model selection process described in Appendix 1.

```
rf_max6 = RandomForestClassifier(max_depth = 6, random_state = 42)
```

4.2. Model Outcome Analysis

The performance of the fitted `rf_max6` on the training data is summarized in Table 2:

Metric	AUPRC	F1_Score	Precision	Recall
Test Data	0.12	0.91	0.96	0.88

Table 2: Performance of rf_max6

Out of the four metrics in the table 2 above we will focus on the F1_score and the AUPRC. Indeed, due to the severe imbalance¹ in the credit card fraud use case data, these two metrics are often considered to be more appropriate than the Precision and Recall because they account for both precision and recall metrics.

In general, when the model’s statistical performance is reasonably strong and/or better than that of the available alternative (criterion #2), the model is approved for continued use. In Salami et al (2024), we noted that this basis for accepting the continued model use during both the development and the monitoring phases is insufficient as it completely ignores the business KPI which reflects the business leaders’ gauge of the model effectiveness. Instead, the evaluation of model performance before and after its development should be guided by both criterion #1 and criterion #2. Otherwise, the consequences can involve significant waste of time, resources or significant financial loss depending on the model’s applications.

4.3. Linking the statistical performance to the business KPI

The business leaders, in their capacity of model owner in many organizations, often hold a higher authority over the data scientist as to whether the model is meeting the target business objective. Therefore, **we consider the business KPI to be a constraint**. Then, the task becomes to find a statistical performance metric that can concur with this business KPI such that an improvement or deterioration in the business KPI can be traced back to the model.

Let’s illustrate our proposal with the credit card fraud use case described in section 4.1. Consider the following hypothetical cost structure 1, which describes the average business cost estimated for the model errors by the business leaders:

Cost structure 1: FP more costly than FN

- \$0 = cost of a True negative or TN (the model accurately identifies a valid transaction)
- \$3 = cost of a False Negative or FN (the model flags a fraudulent transaction as valid)
- \$0 = cost of a True Positive or TP (the model accurately flags a fraudulent transaction)
- \$60² = cost of a False Positive or FP (the model flags a valid transaction as fraudulent)

¹ The proportion of fraud cases is 3.5% which is very small and indicative of an imbalanced dataset.

² In reality, FN is typically more costly than FP in the case of credit card fraud as discussed in section 5.2.

We can then compute for a given data sample³, the statistical performance metric value, and the associated business cost in terms of loss amount from credit card fraud. The figure 1 below shows the relationship between these two performance measures.

Figure 1: Relationship between credit card fraud loss amount and AUPRC in cost structure 1

The expectation in linking the statistical performance metric (x-axis) to the business KPI (y-axis) is to establish a monotonic relationship between these two measures. For the fraud use case under study, this monotonic relationship would signal that a decrease in the fraud loss amount would correspond to an increase in the model’s performance.

For AUPRC as the measure of the model’s statistical performance, while the Figure 1 above shows the expected negative relationship, the monotonic relationship with the fraud loss amount is rather weak as measured by the 15.68% R^2 . At first, this result may be surprising considering that the AUPRC is often recommended when measuring the performance of a binary classifier on severely imbalanced data like the credit card data under consideration.

But, as we revisit the definition of the AUPRC, we realize that this metric is mainly focused on the positive class [5], which may explain why it does not show the strong monotonic relationship we are seeking with the business KPI. To proceed, we investigate the second statistical performance measure in Table 2, namely the $F1_score (F_1)$, which is also recommended for imbalanced data.

³ The modeling data are grouped in 36 samples by order of transaction time, each containing 12,500 credit card transactions.

Figure 2: Relationship between credit card fraud loss amounts and F_1 in cost structure 1

Figure 2 shows the same negative relationship but also a stronger monotonic and linear relationships between the fraud loss amounts and F_1 ($R^2 = 63\%$) than that observed between the same fraud loss amounts and AUPRC in Figure 1. This is an encouraging observation considering the F_1 is a particular form of F_β score⁴ [6] and [7]:

$$F_\beta = (1 + \beta^2) * \frac{\text{precision} * \text{recall}}{(\beta^2 * \text{precision}) + \text{recall}} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

In particular, when:

$$\beta = 1: F_1 = (1 + 1^2) * \frac{\text{precision} * \text{recall}}{(1^2 * \text{precision}) + \text{recall}} = 2 * \frac{\text{precision} * \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}} = \frac{\frac{1}{\text{recall}} + \frac{1}{\text{precision}}}{2} \quad \text{Equation 5.1}$$

$$\beta = 2: F_2 = (1 + 2^2) * \frac{\text{precision} * \text{recall}}{(2^2 * \text{precision}) + \text{recall}} = 5 * \frac{\text{precision} * \text{recall}}{(4 * \text{precision}) + \text{recall}} = \frac{\frac{5}{4} + \frac{1}{\text{precision}}}{\text{recall} + \text{precision}} \quad \text{Equation 5.2}$$

...and so on:

- $F_\beta \rightarrow \text{precision}$ if $\beta \rightarrow 0$ Equation 5.3
- $F_\beta \rightarrow \text{recall}$ if $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ Equation 5.4.

⁴ In F_β , β indicates the magnitude by which Recall is given more importance than Precision. Please refer to section 5.1. for more clarification about this F_β formula.

When we investigate the relationship between the fraud loss amounts and F_β for different values of β , we observe an interesting trend as shown in figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Relationship between fraud loss amount and various forms of F_β in cost structure 1

Figure 3 shows the monotonic relationship with a downward slope that we are seeking. For the credit card fraud use case; this relationship is linear and gets stronger from F_1 to F_4 as illustrated by the regression's R^2 and slope. In Salami et al (2024), we proposed a methodology to find the optimal β value for which the linear and monotonic relationship between the business KPI (fraud loss amount) and the statistical performance metric (F_β) is the strongest. But our analysis was based on the weighted F_β . In the current paper, we discussed the rationale for selecting the weighted F_β over the unweighted F_β .

5. Understanding F_β

5.1. Revisiting F_β formula

Recall equation 5 in section 4.3

$$F_\beta = (1 + \beta^2) * \frac{\text{precision} * \text{recall}}{(\beta^2 * \text{precision}) + \text{recall}} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

This formula shows F_β as the weighted harmonic mean of the precision and recall metrics but the following implementation of F_β in Python provides more insight into the parameters involved in its calculation [9]:

$$F_\beta = fbeta_score(y_true, y_pred, *, beta, labels = "...", pos_label = "...", average = '...', sample_weight = "...", zero_division = '...') \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

In particular, for the “average” parameter, the documentation of scikit-learn package in python lists the following values [9]:

- micro: *calculate metrics globally by counting the total true positives, false negatives and false positives.*
- macro: *calculate metrics for each label and find their unweighted mean. This does not take label imbalance into account*
- samples: *calculate metrics for each instance, and find their average*
- weighted: *calculate metrics for each label, and find their average weighted by support (the number of true instances for each label)*
- binary: *only report results for the class specified by pos_label*

The same documentation also clarifies that the selection of the ‘weighted’ average can account for the class imbalance in the data [9]. This is an important clarification because the equation 5 assumes that the value of the average parameter is “macro” for target label=1. The mathematical expression for the weighted F_β can be found in Equation 10 in Section 6.

5.2. Choosing weighted F_β over unweighted F_β

For the fraud dataset that we used for illustration, the 20,663 fraudulent transactions represent only 3.5% of all transactions under consideration (590,540). This is a good example of class imbalance on which we can evaluate the above guidance in scikit-learn around the appropriateness of weighted F_β over unweighted F_β .

Figure 4: Comparing the impact of unweighted F_β against weighted F_β on R^2

We plotted R^2 (measuring the strength of the linear relationship between F_β and the fraud loss amount) for various values of β . The results are displayed in Figure 4 for four scenarios. For the scenario title M20R, illustrated by the chart on the upper left quadrant, we assumed that the cost of a false positive (FP) is 20 times the cost of a false negative. We can observe that for almost each value of β , the weighted F_β leads to a higher R^2 than the unweighted F_β . This observation is consistent with the guidance in scikit-learn. It can also be noted that this observation holds in other scenarios although the difference in R^2 decreases as we move from scenario M20R to each of the other three scenarios, M20, M5 or M10. In fact, the direction of the difference in R^2 even slightly flips from M20R to M10. This is an interesting finding as it suggests that the selection of the weighted F_β over the unweighted F_β should not only be driven by the class imbalance but also by the relative weight (i.e., the cost ratio in this fraud use case) between false positives and false negatives.

6. Would F_β ever be a “perfect” metric to represent the business KPI? A theoretical consideration of their relationship.

Our business KPI is a linear combination of numbers of false positives and negatives, and while F_β is certainly related to it as empirically shown previously, would F_β (or its transformation) be a “perfect” metric to represent the business KPI?

Theorem 1: The “perfect” metric that represents the business KPI is a function of F_β and the number of true positives (TP).

More formally, since the fraud loss amount (business KPI) is a linear combination of numbers of false positives and false negatives, it can be expressed as:

$\lambda_{FN}FN + \lambda_{FP}FP = (\lambda_{FN} + \lambda_{FP}) \left(\frac{\lambda_{FN}}{\lambda_{FN} + \lambda_{FP}} FN + \frac{\lambda_{FP}}{\lambda_{FN} + \lambda_{FP}} FP \right)$, where λ_{FN} and $\lambda_{FP} \geq 0$, which is simply a positive multiplier times a convex combination of the false positive and false negative quantities. Ignoring the positive multiplier, which is a scaling factor, the following can be proved:

$$TP \left(\frac{1}{F_\beta} - 1 \right) = \tau FN + (1 - \tau) FP \quad (\text{Equation 7})$$

where

$$\tau = \frac{\beta^2}{1 + \beta^2} \in [0,1].$$

And given the value of τ , $\beta = \sqrt{\frac{\tau}{1-\tau}}$ (Equation 8)⁵ where $\beta \geq 0$.

Proof:

From Equation 5,

$$\begin{aligned} F_\beta &= (1 + \beta^2) * \frac{\text{precision} * \text{recall}}{(\beta^2 * \text{precision}) + \text{recall}} = \frac{1}{\frac{\beta^2}{1 + \beta^2} \frac{1}{\text{recall}} + \frac{1}{1 + \beta^2} \frac{1}{\text{precision}}} \\ &= \frac{1}{\tau \frac{1}{\text{recall}} + (1 - \tau) \frac{1}{\text{precision}}} = \frac{1}{\tau \frac{TP + FN}{TP} + (1 - \tau) \frac{TP + FP}{TP}} \\ &= \frac{TP}{TP + \tau FN + (1 - \tau) FP} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\tau FN + (1 - \tau) FP}{TP}} \quad (\text{Equation 9}) \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging: $TP \left(\frac{1}{F_\beta} - 1 \right) = \tau FN + (1 - \tau) FP$ (Equation 7)

As a numerical example, consider Cost Structure 2 in Appendix 2:

- \$0 = cost of a True negative or TN (the model accurately identifies a valid transaction)
- \$60 = cost of a False Negative or FN (the model flags a fraudulent transaction as valid)
- \$0 = cost of a True Positive or TP (the model accurately flags a fraudulent transaction)
- \$3 = cost of a False Positive or FP (the model flags a valid transaction as fraudulent)

⁵ β would be set to ∞ if $\tau = 1$.

This means the fraud loss amount or business KPI = $60FN + 3FP = 63 \left(\frac{60}{63}FN + \frac{3}{63}FP \right)$. Ignoring the scaling factor 63, we have $\tau = \frac{60}{63}$, which implies $\beta = 4.472$ by Equation 7. As a result, the fraud loss amount can be expressed as $TP \left(\frac{1}{F_{4.472}} - 1 \right)$ by Equation 7.

The implication of Equation 6 or 10 is that while F_β is inversely related to the fraud loss, the number of true positives (TP) will need to be included to fully complete the expression (unless TP is about the same across the samples). When possible, one may optimize and measure the business KPI directly (see, for example, Lo & Pachamanova (2023) [8]).

Theorem 1 is only correct if the standard F_β is used. In our analysis in Section 4, we consider the weighted F_β defined as:

$$\text{weighted } F_\beta = \frac{PF_\beta(1) + NF_\beta(0)}{n}, \quad (\text{Equation 10})$$

where $F_\beta(1) = F_\beta$, the standard metric with 1 as the target label, $F_\beta(0)$ is the mirror metric using 0 as the target label (i.e., flipping the roles of 1 and 0) and is defined as:

$$F_\beta(0) = (1 + \beta^2) * \frac{\text{precision}(0) * \text{recall}(0)}{(\beta^2 * \text{precision}(0)) + \text{recall}(0)}, \quad (\text{Equation 11})$$

where $\text{precision}(0)$ and $\text{recall}(0)$ are defined such that the target label is 0, P and N are number of actual positives and negatives, respectively, and $n = P + N =$ the overall sample size.

If $N \gg P$, the above weighted F_β is dominated by $F_\beta(0)$, which is indeed our empirical case (as $\frac{N}{P} = 28.6$). Let us then examine $F_\beta(0)$ in the following.

Theorem 2

$$TN \left(\frac{1}{F_\beta(0)} - 1 \right) = \tau FP + (1 - \tau) FN \quad (\text{Equation 12})$$

where

$$\tau = \frac{\beta^2}{1 + \beta^2} \in [0, 1].$$

As before, given the value of τ , $\beta = \sqrt{\frac{\tau}{1-\tau}}$ (Equation 8)⁶ where $\beta \geq 0$.

⁶ β would be set to ∞ if $\tau = 1$.

Proof:

From Equation 11,

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{\beta}(0) &= (1 + \beta^2) * \frac{\text{precision}(0) * \text{recall}(0)}{(\beta^2 * \text{precision}(0)) + \text{recall}(0)} \\
 &= \frac{1}{\frac{\beta^2}{1 + \beta^2} \frac{1}{\text{recall}(0)} + \frac{1}{1 + \beta^2} \frac{1}{\text{precision}(0)}} \\
 &= \frac{1}{\tau \frac{1}{\text{recall}(0)} + (1 - \tau) \frac{1}{\text{precision}(0)}} = \frac{1}{\tau \frac{TN + FP}{TN} + (1 - \tau) \frac{TN + FN}{TN}} \\
 &= \frac{TN}{TN + \tau FP + (1 - \tau) FN} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\tau FP + (1 - \tau) FN}{TN}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Rearranging: } TN \left(\frac{1}{F_{\beta}(0)} - 1 \right) = \tau FP + (1 - \tau) FN \quad (\text{Equation 12}).$$

Equation 12 indicates that while $F_{\beta}(0)$ is also inversely related to the fraud loss (a weighted sum of numbers of false positives and false negatives), the number of true negatives (TN) will need to be included to fully complete the expression (unless TN is about the same across samples).

Since $\frac{1}{F_{\beta}(0)}$ can be expressed as the following Taylor Series⁷:

$$\frac{1}{F_{\beta}(0)} = 1 - (F_{\beta}(0) - 1) + (F_{\beta}(0) - 1)^2 - (F_{\beta}(0) - 1)^3 + \dots,$$

linearizing the component in the parentheses on the left-hand side of Equation 12 would reduce the equation to⁸:

$$TN (1 - F_{\beta}(0)) \approx \tau FP + (1 - \tau) FN.$$

Or,

$$F_{\beta}(0) \approx 1 - \frac{1}{TN} [\tau FP + (1 - \tau) FN]. \quad (\text{Equation 13})$$

Equation 12 shows that when plotting $F_{\beta}(0)$ against the fraud loss, we would expect a downward sloping relationship, as seen in previous graphs in this paper. Again, because of the presence of TN , the above relationship is not deterministic (unless TN has low variability across samples).

Similarly, $TP \left(\frac{1}{F_{\beta}} - 1 \right) = \tau FN + (1 - \tau) FP$ in Equation 7 from Theorem 1 can also be linearly approximated as:

$$F_{\beta} = F_{\beta}(1) \approx 1 - \frac{1}{TP} [\tau FN + (1 - \tau) FP]. \quad (\text{Equation 14})$$

⁷ The convergence condition for this series is $|F_{\beta}(0) - 1| < 1$ or $0 < F_{\beta}(0) < 2$, which is easily satisfied with this metric.

⁸ The error term is dominated by $(F_{\beta}(0) - 1)^2$ which is very small when $F_{\beta}(0)$ is close to 1.

Hence, both $F_\beta(0)$ and $F_\beta(1)$ can be approximately written as linearly and negatively related to a weighted sum of FN and FP (in Equations 12 & 13), and so is weighted F_β as it is simply a weighted average of $F_\beta(0)$ and $F_\beta(1)$, as seen in Equation 10. Thus, the downward sloping relationship is still approximately correct even in more general scenarios where $N \gg P$ does not hold.

7. Conclusion and next steps

In this paper, we build on our previous findings in Salami et al (2024) [1] that show limitations in evaluating the performance of a model based on statistical metrics alone. Considering models do not exist in isolation but operate within a broader business context, it is important to link the model’s statistical performance to the business KPI that drive the business decisions. However, selecting the appropriate statistical performance metric among the plethora of candidates proposed by the literature remains an interesting research field. Our paper aims at contributing to this research by examining the F_β . We showed that while, in general, the guidance in scikit-learn that recommends the weighted F_β over the unweighted F_β in the presence of class imbalance is reasonable, it should also account for the ratio of the weights assigned to false positives and false negatives. We believe that our proposal can conceptually be strengthened further by demonstrating mathematically that it is agnostic to the dataset used.

Appendix 1: Model selection

The random forest rf_max6 was selected over the other two candidates due to its higher precision, recall or F1:

- DTC_ent5 = DecisionTreeClassifier (criterion= ‘entropy’, max_depth=5, random_state=42)
- LR = LogisticRegression (random_state=42)

Scorer/Metric	0	1	Accuracy	Macro avg	Weighted average	Classifier
precision	0.98	0.14	0.86	0.56	0.96	DTC_ent5
Recall	0.86	0.63	0.86	0.75	0.86	DTC_ent5
F1_score	0.92	0.23	0.86	0.58	0.90	DTC_ent5
precision	0.98	0.13	0.88	0.56	0.95	Lr_lbfgs
Recall	0.90	0.43	0.88	0.66	0.88	Lr_lbfgs
F1_score	0.94	0.20	0.88	0.57	0.91	Lr_lbfgs
precision	0.99	0.17	0.88	0.58	0.96	Rf_max6
Recall	0.89	0.63	0.88	0.76	0.88	Rf_max6
F1_score	0.94	0.27	0.88	0.60	0.91	Rf_max6

Appendix 2: Cost structures

In Salami et al [1], we discussed the following three cost structures in addition to cost structure 1 described in section 4.3.

The cost structure 1 assumes that the business cost of a false positive (FP) is 20 times that of a false negative (FN). For the credit card fraud use case the inverse is more likely as, in general, the financial loss resulting from the occurrence of fraud is much greater than that resulting from declining a valid transaction based on fraud suspicion. For illustration purpose, let us consider the following cost structures 2, 3 and 4 in which a FN costs more than a FP:

M20 (Cost structure 2):

- \$0 = cost of a True negative or TN (the model accurately identifies a valid transaction)
- \$60 = cost of a False Negative or FN (the model flags a fraudulent transaction as valid)
- \$0 = cost of a True Positive or TP (the model accurately flags a fraudulent transaction)
- \$3 = cost of a False Positive or FP (the model flags a valid transaction as fraudulent)

The link between the β values and the R_β^2 in the cost structure 2 is shown in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: Relationship between β and R_β^2 in cost structure 2 for $\beta \geq 0$

M10 (Cost structure 3):

- \$0 = cost of a True negative or TN (the model accurately identifies a valid transaction)
- \$50 = cost of a False Negative or FN (the model flags a fraudulent transaction as valid)

- \$0 = cost of a True Positive or TP (the model accurately flags a fraudulent transaction)
- \$5 = cost of a False Positive or FP (the model flags a valid transaction as fraudulent)

Figure 6 below shows the relationship between β and R_β^2 when the weight ratio is 10 in favor of the FN.

Figure 6: Relationship between β and R_β^2 in cost structure 3 for $\beta \geq 0$

M5 (Cost structure 4):

- \$0 = cost of a True negative or TN (the model accurately identifies a valid transaction)
- \$40 = cost of a False Negative or FN (the model flags a fraudulent transaction as valid)
- \$0 = cost of a True Positive or TP (the model accurately flags a fraudulent transaction)
- \$8 = cost of a False Positive or FP (the model flags a valid transaction as fraudulent)

Figure 7: Relationship between β and R_β^2 in cost structure 5 for $\beta \geq 0$

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